

Electrode effects revisited

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Abstract: Electrode effects are often observed as an instrumental artifact associated with measurements of electrical permittivity at low frequencies. Such effects introduce a polarization capacity, C_p , associated with the interface between the electrode and the material under test. This polarization capacity follows a fractional power law dependence on frequency, such that $C_p \propto \omega^{-\alpha}$, where ω is the frequency and α is a function of frequency with values below 1/2. The possibility that such a power law dependence may be attributed to coupling between the applied electric field and the free charge in the Debye layer is examined.

Introduction

The term electrode effects is used here to identify a broad class of phenomena associated with the electrical properties of an interface between dissimilar materials. These effects may be realized by measurement of a polarization capacity, C_p , or a polarization resistance, R_p , over and above the electrical properties of the bulk material. Such electrode effects often confound the accurate measurement of electrical properties at low frequencies [1] and are thus of both practical and fundamental interest.

The interface between an electrode and a weak electrolyte or dielectric material may be modeled by the equivalent circuit shown in Figure 1. It should be noted that there is no path for direct current in the figure and that the circuit shown is blocking for direct currents. The current associated with this blocking circuit is sometimes referred to as faradaic. A resistive path in parallel with C_p may be included to model non-faradaic currents. Non-faradaic currents may include, for example, currents due to electrochemical reactions [2]. As we are primarily interested in the case where electrochemical reactions may be neglected, this discussion is limited to such conditions.

The measured polarization capacity, C_p , obtained for a dilute solution of KCl in CH_3OH [3] is shown in Figure 2. Two distinct regions are identi-

Figure 1: Equivalent circuit for an electrode interface. The bulk material is characterized by a capacity, C_0 , and resistance, R_0 , while the electrical properties of the electrode interface are characterized by a polarization capacity, C_p , and a polarization resistance, R_p .

fied by these data: for frequencies below 4 KHz the slope of the curve is -1/4, while at higher frequencies the slope of the curve decreases and approaches a value of -1/2. These data are empirically fit by an expression of the form $C_p \propto \omega^{-\alpha}$, where ω is the frequency and α is a positive, real function of frequency with values less than or equal to 1/2. Scheider [3] observes that this fractional power frequency dependence is obtained under a broad range of conditions and posits that such a power law dependence is inherent to the electrode interface. We advocate this premise here as well.

In this report, we examine the theoretical basis for the classical dispersion equations, that is, the Debye, Cole-Cole, and Davidson-Cole equations, and argue that a proper generalization of the methods underlying these equations leads to the above noted fractional power frequency dependence.

Figure 2: Polarization capacity, C_p , obtained for a dilute solution of KCl in CH_3OH [3].

The dispersion equations

The classical dispersion equations may be realized by stereographic projection of the Riemann sphere, S^2 , onto the complex plane. This scenario is shown in Figure 3, where we associate $\mathbb{C} \times \mathbb{R}$ with a real, Euclidean 3-space, \mathbb{R}^3 . The complex plane is identified with $\mathbb{C} \times \{0\}$ and the north and south poles of the unit sphere are identified with $p_+ = (0, 1)$ and $p_- = (0, -1)$, respectively. The Riemann sphere,

$$S^2 = \{(z, t) \in \mathbb{C} \times \mathbb{R} \mid |z|^2 + t^2 = 1\}, \quad (1)$$

may be viewed as a geometric representation of the metric condition on the propagation of electromagnetic fields.

The projection $\psi_+(p)$ shown in Figure 3, maps points $p \in S^2$ onto the complex plane by projection of p through p_+ [7]. It may be noted that there is an equivalent projection $\psi_-(-p)$ of $-p$ through p_- , that is $\psi_+(p) = -\psi_-(-p)$. There is thus a formal equivalence between antipodal points in S^2 and a two-to-one, onto correspondence between points in the Riemann sphere and points in the complex plane. The dispersion equations make explicit use of this double cover on S^2 to provide expressions for the real and imaginary parts of the complex permittivity, ϵ^* . The projection onto the real axis,

$$\frac{1}{2}(\psi_+ - \bar{\psi}_-) = \frac{1}{2}(\epsilon^* + \bar{\epsilon}^*) : S^2 \longrightarrow \mathbb{R},$$

results in a locus of points corresponding to a straight line with intercept ϵ_0 . The projection onto the imaginary axis,

$$\frac{1}{2}(\psi_+ - \bar{\psi}_-) = \frac{1}{2}(\epsilon^* - \bar{\epsilon}^*) : S^2 \longrightarrow i\mathbb{R},$$

produces a circle in the complex plane. Since the position the real and imaginary axes are arbitrary, the Riemann sphere, or indeed any closed, oriented 2-surface, is homeomorphic to the disjoint union of an open disc and the unit circle [4].

We summarize the classical dispersion equations with a commutative diagram:

$$\begin{array}{ccc} \{S^2\} & \xrightarrow{F} & \{S^2\} \\ \downarrow \pi_1(S^2) & & \downarrow g\pi_1(S^2) \\ H_c^q(\mathbb{R}^2) & \xrightarrow{i_*} & H^q(\mathbb{C}\mathbb{P}^1). \end{array}$$

In the diagram, $\{S^2\}$ denotes the category of topological spaces homeomorphic to S^2 , and F is any homomorphism $F : S^2 \longrightarrow S^2$. The de Rham cohomology group [7], which is 2-dimensional vector

Figure 3: Stereographic projections $\psi_+(p)$ and $\psi_-(-p) : S^2 \longrightarrow \mathbb{C} \times \{0\}$.

space with values in the space of real, analytic functions, is indicated by $H_c^q(\mathbb{R}^2)$. We denote by $\mathbb{C}\mathbb{P}^1$ the complex projective space [7] and by $H^q(\mathbb{C}\mathbb{P}^1)$ the cohomology group. $\mathbb{C}\mathbb{P}^n$ formally identifies the set of 1-dimensional subspaces of the complex Euclidean space \mathbb{C}^{n+1} and is, in general, a complex analytic n -manifold. The fundamental group π_1 is functorial from the category of topological spaces to the category of groups, and i^* is an inclusion.

The metric condition [1] enforces an equivalence on S^2 . In general, for associated topological spaces $X, Y \subset S^2$ there is an equivalence $X \sim Y$ defined by $X = Y$ and $X = -Y$. We may associate X and Y , for example, with the upper and lower hemispheres or with semicircles on the unit circle.

In general, the volume form for a complex projective space, $\mathbb{C}\mathbb{P}^n$, is proportion to ω^n [7]. Integration over the volume yields the energy, and the normalization, that is the energy capacity C , is proportional to ω^{-n} .

Free charge

The charge density ρ within the Debye layer is, in general, non-zero, and this free charge is coupled to an externally applied electric field. The distribution of free charge associated with an electrode interface thus depends on the applied electric field.

For a uniform applied electric field, the deformation of the native charge distribution is essentially a dilation along the normal to the electrode surface. This deformation can be visualized by the inflation of a ball with the positions of the poles held fixed: It may be noted that the fibration of the ball, that is the description of the surface of the ball by lines of latitude and longitude, for example, is invariant under a change in the state of inflation. The

difference between the original ball and the inflated ball is thus homeomorphic to a 2-torus, T^2 [6].

By assumption, the metric condition associated with the propagation of electromagnetic fields through the material is invariant, thus any deformation associated with the Reimann sphere must be transverse to the sphere. We then associate the coupling of free charge with a multiplication of coordinates, $S^1 \times \mathbb{C}\mathbb{P}^1 \subset \mathbb{C}^3$. The Reimann sphere is embedded in a higher dimensional space, $S^2 \subset S^3 \subset \mathbb{C}^3$. The proper generalization of the dispersion equations to the case of coupled free charge is thus by a projection $\mathbb{C}^3 \rightarrow \mathbb{C}\mathbb{P}^2$.

The time evolution of charge density may be represented by an orbit $f : S^1 \rightarrow \mathbb{C}^3$. In the absence of charge injection, the net charge associated with the Debye layer is conserved, and the condition of charge conservation is satisfied if $f(0) = f(2\pi) = \rho_0$. It may be noted that the condition of charge conservation, indeed any conserved quantity, implicitly defines a metric condition. In this case, the 2-surface $T^2 = S^1 \times \mathbb{C}\mathbb{P}^1 \subset S^3$ is associated with the conservation of charge.

The T^2 surface may be described by closed S^1 orbits of rational slope or by open S^1 orbits of irrational slope with a limit cycle. The limit cycle is associated with the condition $\rho = 0$. Now T^2 is a closed oriented 2-surface and thus is homeomorphic to the disjoint union of the limit cycle associated with the condition $\rho = 0$ and an open disc. Finally \mathbb{R}^2 is homeomorphic to the hyperbolic plane \mathbb{H}^2 [6], that is the unit circle is associated with the boundary of an infinite 2-surface.

Discussion

In closing, we mention several related observations:

Conservation of charge is an underlying physical principle, which would suggest that the associated toroidal geometry is invariant. That is, the toroidal structure associated with charge conservation may persist even under conditions of charge injection and conduction. The analysis presented further suggests that the permittivity tensor, and thus the index of refraction, conforms to the toroidal geometry. These conclusions are born out by experimental observations [9] that show the index of refraction in a dielectric fluid subjected to a uniform electric field to have hexagonal coordination in a plane perpendicular to the field for conditions near the onset of electrically driven convective flow and charge conduction. The data presented show the plane perpendicular to the applied electric field to

be covered by regular hexagonal cells with a toroidal structure included in each cell. This would suggest that there is a close connection between the flow of charge the physical presence of the toroidal structure.

The analysis presented suggests the exact cohomology sequence

$$H_c^q(\mathbb{R}^{2n}) \xrightarrow{i^*} H^q(\mathbb{C}\mathbb{P}^n) \xrightarrow{j^*} H^q(\mathbb{C}\mathbb{P}^{n-1}), \quad (2)$$

where j^* is an integration isomorphism. The cohomology group $H^q(\mathbb{C}\mathbb{P}^{n-1})$ suggests a projection onto the real axis for $n = 2$ that is linear in ω^2 with intercept λ_0 . The real number λ_0 may be associated with the diameter of the toroid. This would imply that there is a well defined spatial dimension associated with the onset of charge conduction under conditions of convection flow. Conversely, the present of a physical structure that supports a circulating current in a plane normal to the applied electric field may enable charge conduction.

Scheider [3] proposes a fractal model to describe the observed dependence of C_p on frequency. In his model, the electrode is connected to the bulk material through an infinite network of self-similar paths. The model further associates these current paths with the inherent roughness of the electrode surface. The geometric interpretation presented here implies a tiling of the \mathbb{R}^2 or \mathbb{H}^2 planes by regular polygons [6]. This tiling suggests the existence of an infinite network of self-similar structures on the plane. The fractal behavior noted in the polarization capacity is then associated here with the tiling of the plane rather than with the nature of the electrode surface. Close examination of the data presented by Scheider and indeed the analysis given by Fricke [10] suggests that the low frequency fractional power dependence is well represented by rational numbers: The data presented by Scheider show values for α of 1/4 and 1/5, and the analysis presented by Fricke suggests values for α of 1/3, 1/4, 1/5, 1/7, and 1/8. The restriction of α to the rational numbers is consistent with a tiling of the plane by regular polygons.

Conclusions

The fractional power frequency dependence noted for the polarization capacity of an electrode interface appears to be consistent with the geometry of charge coupled flow. The $-1/4$ power law noted at low frequencies is associated with a global charge conservation in which the interface is blocking to dc currents. The $-1/2$ power law noted at higher fre-

quencies is associated with local charge conservation and with the onset of electrically driven convection flow and of charge flow.

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